

EXPLORING THE NARRATIVES OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE FIRST DISTRICT OF LAGUNA: BASIS FOR AN INCLUSIVITY WORKSHOP

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ABSTRACT

Insufficient government support and neglect of their current circumstances have intensified challenges for special education (SPED) teachers in the country. This qualitative study explored the narratives of ten SPED teachers in San Pedro, Biñan, and Sta. Rosa, Laguna focusing on their challenges, student relationships, and collaborations with parents and professionals. Through purposive sampling and one-on-one semi-structured interviews, recurring themes and concepts were identified using thematic analysis. Findings revealed that teaching under the SPED program means innovating teaching materials, facing various hurdles, and finding hope and motivation in the students themselves. There were five themes that emerged from special education as a career, such as “strong relationships with students”, “utilization of diverse interventions”, “sense of vocational calling”, “job fulfillment”, and “motivation in teaching”. While themes such as “physical aggression from students”, “lack of resources”, “heavy workload”, “conflicts among co-workers”, “limited number of teachers”, and “lack of administrative support” pertains to the challenges encountered by teachers. Moreover, teachers are involved in collaboration with parents and professionals, including “parent-teacher conferences”, “day-to-day assessments and feedback”, “consultation with experts or specialists”, and “established medical centers”. Sometimes these teachers experience “negative encounters with parents”. The key findings suggest that the government and administrators should establish an inclusivity workshop for special education teachers and distribute proper funding to ease the jobs of teachers. Parents and regular teachers

should also collaborate with SPED teachers to enhance their children's learning experience.

Keywords: *Special Education Teachers, Narratives, Challenges, Inclusivity Workshop, First District of Laguna*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching within the special education (SPED) curriculum is among the most challenging vocations, demanding specialized expertise and understanding, along with a profound sense of care, enthusiasm, and commitment to both the profession and the students with special needs (Webb, 2023). Nonetheless, SPED teachers in the Philippines encounter a range of obstacles that compound their challenges, including insufficient governmental and administrative support and neglect of their current circumstances. A report by Luna (2022), published in Philstar, highlights the government's failure to adequately allocate funds to SPED centers and schools. Furthermore, Balading et al. (2023) underscore that this lack of governmental support has resulted in teacher burnout, hindering their ability to enjoy life beyond their professional duties. Recognizing the narratives of SPED teachers, the hurdles they confront, and their collaborative efforts to better assist their students is crucial for raising awareness, particularly among the government, about the necessary programs to improve their circumstances.

As stated by Allam and Martin (2021), empathy lies at the heart of special education. By creating a safe and inclusive environment, special education fosters a sense of belonging and support for its students. Special education is an educational approach that focuses on meeting the specific needs of students with disabilities or diverse learning styles. When it comes to the lived experiences of SPED teachers, it is all about understanding the unique challenges and rewards they encounter in their profession. They play a crucial role in creating inclusive learning environments and helping students reach their full potential.

Special educators' perspectives are crucial in shaping the field of special education. Their firsthand experiences and insights provide a unique lens through which they can better understand the needs and challenges of students with disabilities. Magsambol (2020) found that educating students with special needs differs significantly from teaching ordinary students. Only SPED teachers embrace this unique difference and approach their classrooms with a specialized mindset. They undergo specialized training and professional development to enhance their knowledge and skills in areas such as behavior management, assistive technology, and individualized instruction. Additionally, SPED teachers demonstrate patience, empathy, and a genuine passion for advocating for their students' educational rights and fostering inclusive learning environments.

SPED teachers work with students who have diverse learning needs and abilities. Understanding the lived experiences of these teachers involves exploring the challenges

they face, the strategies they use, and the impact of their work on students' lives. For instance, SPED teachers, who may find themselves in classrooms without support staff, are responsible for teaching 20 students with diverse special needs that require personalized instruction. On top of that, they may have a caseload of 20 students who need individualized education programs (IEPs), annual testing, and regular meetings with parents and other teachers. According to Allison Academy (2023), to meet specific student needs, an individualized educational plan (IEP) is created for each child with learning disabilities. This way, the school designs an educational plan they need to implement based on the identified disability. Moreover, it is crucial for SPED teachers to meet deadlines and submit necessary paperwork, as failing to do so can have legal implications. This adds even more pressure on them.

Teacher preparation programs and professional development aim to equip educators with the necessary skills to create inclusive learning environments for all students. However, many of these programs still face challenges in effectively preparing general educators to interact with students with special needs in a regular classroom setting (Ingvarson et al., 2014; Rock et al., 2016). While methods of working with students with special needs are often covered in these programs, teachers still require assistance in understanding the specific knowledge and skills they need to effectively support students with special needs (Harper & De Jong, 2009). Even though the government has presented programs to alleviate the burdens of SPED teachers, many individuals still lack knowledge about how to support them and their students. Additionally, there is limited study and literature concerning the lived experiences of SPED teachers in the Philippines, especially in the first district of Laguna. Through this study and the implementation of inclusivity workshops in the cities of San Pedro, Biñan, and Sta. Rosa, it aims to improve understanding of how these teachers can navigate and overcome the diverse obstacles they encounter.

Research Questions

This study seeks to delve into the narratives of SPED teachers in the first district of Laguna. Therefore, this study will investigate:

1. What are the narratives of special education teachers?

Moreover, the researchers formulated possible narratives assuming: (1) The SPED teachers have developed close relationships with parents that help learning among students; (2) The SPED teachers offer their students great individualized teaching and support; (3) The SPED teachers demonstrate their ability to provide instruction to their students with less equipment; (4) The SPED teachers are having difficulties meeting the needs of the children with special needs; (5) The SPED teachers feel as if they are not good enough when their students face continued discrimination upon entering inclusive classrooms; (6) The SPED teachers collaborate with professionals such as psychotherapists and other teachers to support students with special needs; (7) The SPED teachers are fulfilled with their jobs; (8) The SPED teachers are under increased strain due to their working conditions; (9) The SPED teachers feel that they need to keep

improving their skills to help their students better, and; (10) The SPED teachers believe in the potential of every student, regardless of their challenges.

METHODOLOGY

Scope and Delimitation

This study explored and examined the lived experiences of special education teachers who work in private or public schools within the first district of Laguna, encompassing San Pedro, Biñan, and Santa Rosa. This research studied the special education teachers' narratives, including their relationships with their students with special needs, their collaboration with the parents of the students and other professionals for support, their ability to instruct, their faced challenges, and their employed coping mechanisms to navigate through these challenges. Additionally, this research excluded topics related to quantitative variables and approaches, as well as other irrelevant factors, like their economic status, beliefs, and other lived experiences they faced outside their field.

Research Design

The researchers used the Narrative Inquiry approach, which falls under qualitative research (Deakin University, 2024). This approach is particularly suitable for examining human experiences and, in the context of SPED, understanding the perspectives of each teacher regarding their lived experiences. It enables a comprehensive understanding of the interconnected significance of these experiences, revealing their narratives within the context of their professional lives. By understanding their unique stories, the researchers gained valuable insights into how they make meaning on their unique journeys, challenges, and success in the field of special education.

Key Informants of the Study

The researchers selected ten (10) special education teachers as key informants from the first district of Laguna, from the cities of San Pedro, Biñan, and Santa Rosa. The researchers also gathered data in schools that offer SPED programs for the one-on-one semi-structured interviews, from both private and public schools, to prevent biases and to provide strong and sufficient information from SPED teachers.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data gathering begun by conducting a thorough review and analysis of various literature sources, including published books and online articles, to further enhance the depth of understanding by the researchers for their research. The researchers then developed a qualitative researcher-made interview questionnaire, research questions, and instruments which were validated by a psychometrician, senior high school principal, and special education teacher. This process ensured the reliability of the study.

After that, the researchers drafted a consent letter that was submitted to the Divisional Office (DO). After the consent letter, research questionnaires, and research instruments have been validated, the researchers advanced to the Divisional Office to submit the necessary documents to seek the list of SPED schools in the first district of Laguna, which includes San Pedro, Biñan, and Santa Rosa. Upon checking the list of available SPED schools, the researchers selected two institutions for each area of the first district of Laguna.

Subsequently, the researchers sent a letter of consent to the chosen SPED schools via email using electronic consent forms. This communication informed the schools about the study and the upcoming interviews. After waiting for the allotted time for responses, the researchers have taken action based on the two scenarios that emerged. First, if the school has not responded or did not approve of being interviewed, the researchers find another school from the list and will again send an email to await their response. Second, if the school has consented to be interviewed, the researchers proceed to arrange the interview schedule. Furthermore, the researchers selected 10 key informants from the chosen schools in San Pedro, Biñan, and Santa Rosa. The researchers finally chosen the teachers to be interviewed for the study and gave them a letter of consent to ask for their approval to participate as key informants.

During the introduction of the research for the interview, the researchers assured the key informants about the confidentiality of their participation in answering the questionnaire and introduced the purpose of the research to them. Thereafter, the researchers requested a permission to use voice recording and take pictures for documentation following the research protocol. After that, the researchers proceeded with the one-on-one interview and subsequently prepared the research questionnaires. While one researcher conducted the interview, other members recorded the conversation and have taken photos for documentation. Eventually, regarding the questions in the research questionnaire, the researchers inquired about other related topics to broaden the scope of the key informants' responses. The said interview has been conducted with all the group members present on the same day prepared to assist.

After the interview with the key informants, the researchers processed the data, starting with the transcription of collected information. This involved reviewing the voice recording, and transcription to ensure accuracy. Following this, the researchers begun with the coding of the details presented in the data, highlighting the important information from the result of the interview. Henceforth, the researchers analyzed and interpreted the collected data, and drawn conclusions in the study. Upon the processing of the data, the researchers prepared the electronic storage wherein the information have been deleted after the span of 30 days.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized one-on-one semi-structured interviews to obtain information. The key informants have been questioned verbally and individually by the

researchers. The researchers prepared a set of open-ended questions that asked about their lived experiences as a SPED teacher. This approach lets the researchers gathered the information properly about the key informants by having sets of questions, and the researchers could clarify some information due to the interactive feature of semi-structured interviews.

Tests for reliability, inter-rater validation is performed on the research instrument by consulting one licensed psychometrician, one licensed professional special education teacher, and one principal. Additionally, the researchers are strict about ensuring that the right procedures will be followed before, during, and after data collection.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis, as a qualitative data analysis approach, involves scrutinizing a collection of texts, such as interviews or transcripts (Caulfield, 2023). This analytical approach is particularly well-suited, notably within studies where researchers examine detailed responses from key informants, elucidating their lived experiences and challenges. The transcripts of these interviews, containing the verbatim accounts of key informants, undergo thorough review and analysis. Furthermore, through this method, researchers meticulously examined the data to uncover recurring themes, concepts, and underlying structures. This approach aligned with the research instrument employed in the study, namely, one-on-one semi-structured interviews, aiding in addressing the research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1. *Special Education as a Career*

Job fulfillment is the degree of happiness and satisfaction in working. Not focusing on paychecks only, but feeding the sense of purpose that leads to fulfillment (Mannaberg, 2023). Special education teachers showed that despite the challenges, they are satisfied with their jobs. They are fulfilled when they see the children apply what they are learning in terms of intellect and behavior to their parents' testimonials. They see that challenges, no matter how great, could be lessened with time; thus, they treat their students as their own child. Key informant 6 mentioned that they are satisfied with their job, even after working with students with special needs for a long exposure. *"Yes. In-enjoy ko rin kasi 11 years na nga, nakatagal pa ako eh—"* Even though it is tough handling their students, SPED teachers testified that their job is fulfilling. They appreciate even the smallest achievement that each learner shows. Key informants 5, 8, and 10 provided their reasons for this, while according to Key informant 1, *"Napaka fulfilling na bagay na yung simpleng maturuan mong humawak ng lapis ang bata, sobrang fulfilling non. So, all in all, kahit andaming challenges sa SPED pero nakikita pa rin yung kabuuan as magandang bagay so masaya ako ron."* It is an achievement for a teacher for the child to be able to learn what they teach. The fulfillment of the teachers comes from seeing the child actually learn, even in the simplest ways, and is reflected through their actions. Key informants 3 and 7 also justified that parents share their testimonies, that they also see that their children are learning, and that feedback contributes to the satisfaction of the teachers. Seeing their students with a disability achieve is one way to be fulfilled (Grafwallner, 2017; Sands, 2017; Pruitt, 2018), even though pursuing special education might be challenging. Teaching special education can be tremendously rewarding since it fosters creativity and offers chances you may not have imagined. This strengthens assumption 7 because all of the key informants expressed satisfaction and fulfillment in their roles, despite encountering numerous challenges. They emphasized that teaching special education can be highly gratifying as it encourages creativity and presents unexpected opportunities.

Motivation serves as the driving force behind learning, allowing educators to view their role as more than just a job but rather a mission. It is crucial for teaching students effectively with genuine care and enthusiasm (Impact Teachers, 2017). Teaching, whether in a special education setting or in general, demands considerable determination and inspiration to offer optimal support and direction to students. It necessitates patience, understanding, and an authentic enthusiasm for assisting individuals in realizing their utmost capabilities. Key informant 1 regarded teaching in the special education program as a calling, rather than merely a profession, a sentiment that Key informant 2 concurred with. They explained that teaching children with special needs requires a significant amount of motivation, dedication, and passion, stating, *"Sa pagtuturo, once na hindi ka motivated from the heart, hindi ka magiging successful magturo."* They both emphasized that their motivation in teaching these students is to assist them in reaching their full potential despite their disabilities. Key informant 2 also underscored the importance of seeing the capabilities of students rather than focusing solely on their disabilities, saying, *"You see the able in terms of the disabled. You see the ability rather than the disability."* However, Key informant 10 expressed, *"Sad to say, bleak ang future ng mga bata dito,"* reflecting the teachers' concerns regarding the future prospects of their students. Key

informants 4 and 6 argued, though, their aspirations of making progress in their students' lives despite the obstacles they face. Key informant 4 emphasized, "*Yung nakikita mo silang may progress. Kahit konting progress at first. Progress is still progress.*" Key informant 6 then elaborated, "*Ang goal natin is maging independent yung bata, matuto siya ng sarili niya. Not necessarily na acads, yung pansarili lang.*" Therefore, most of the key informants expressed that their motivation for teaching children with special needs stems from their desire to witness these students thriving and achieving success in their future careers. Despite facing numerous challenges as special education teachers, the prospect of seeing these children lead fulfilling lives serves as a driving force to persevere. However, some key informants have acknowledged that due to the severity of certain students' conditions, not all may achieve their desired futures. The results of this study can also be linked to the research of Sturdivant (2017), which highlights the idea that certain special education teachers may become disheartened about their students' future prospects due to the severity of their disabilities. Additionally, it emphasizes the pivotal role of special education instructors in providing guidance aimed at nurturing vital life skills to facilitate students' transition into adulthood. While their motivations for teaching may differ, their steadfast commitment to the advancement and welfare of their students remains unwavering. This contradicts assumption 10 because some of the special education teachers have stated that they do not see the potential of their students due to the severity of their disabilities. However, instead of succumbing to discouragement or regret, these teachers focus on teaching essential life skills and knowledge to the children. Furthermore, this also strengthens assumption 9 as all of the key informants conveyed their desire to continuously enhance their skills to better assist their students. As Key informant 1 put it, "*I need to do more, so I can help them more.*"

A vocational calling is the divine summons for an individual and their life path, typically characterized by stability and enduring permanence throughout one's lifetime. The main factor in why an individual becomes a special education teacher is their background knowledge and experiences as someone who was associated with someone who has a disability, which gives them the drive to pursue it. Key informant 2 viewed teaching in a special education program as a sense of vocational calling, to which Key informant 3 agreed, explaining that being a special education teacher is about dedication and passion to help students with special needs reach their full potential despite their hindrances. They added, "*Parang para sakin ata itong SPED teacher ano?*" Hence, the key informants shared that they had no motive to study special education at first, given the stereotypes and challenges that a special education teacher faced in the country. However, because of the thought that this profession is their 'fate', they embraced the challenge of becoming one. According to Balading et al. (2023), their commitment is associated with their principles and values, therefore, they landed on their careers because of the paths leading them to pursue it.

An educational intervention refers to the measures implemented by school staff to aid a student facing difficulties, which can encompass both instructional and behavioral strategies. Teaching within the special education program necessitates teachers to be flexible and ready to address various disabilities and instructional methods, determining appropriate interventions for individual students. Additionally, it entails understanding and embracing diverse learning styles and communication techniques tailored to each

student. Consequently, special education teachers must possess a profound comprehension of different disabilities and educational tactics, alongside a dedication to creating an inclusive and encouraging learning atmosphere for every student. Key informant 2 claimed that every student with special needs learn differently, to which Key informant 3 agreed, explaining that being an effective special education teacher means finding ways or teaching strategies that will fit a specific student. Key informant 2 stated, *“Iba-iba rin kasi talaga matuto mga bata, may special needs ang mga bata, iba-iba talaga.”* Key informant 3 then added, *“Ang isang bata, hindi dapat pare-parehas ang way ng pagtuturo eh.”* Key informants 5 and 6 discussed, though, the concept of academic modification, which involves adapting the curriculum to suit the intellectual capabilities of students with special needs. Key informant 5 explained, *“We do academic modifications and accommodations depende sa pangangailangan ng bata.”* Key informant 6 further elaborated, *“Syempre iibahin mo yung strategies mo. Ibibigay mo yung magiging interested siya.”* Key informants 4 and 7, on the other hand, employed traditional teaching methods, such as distributing worksheets and adhering to the provided curriculum. They both remarked, *“So kami yung gumagawa ng worksheet na kailangang... na magagamit mo for the whole week.”* Therefore, most of the key informants emphasized the necessity of employing varied teaching strategies tailored to the unique capabilities of each child with special needs. They noted that there is no “one-size-fits-all” intervention, as some students struggle with auditory processing while others have visual difficulties. Additionally, they highlighted the limited attention span of children with special needs, prompting them to utilize diverse manipulative materials and equipment to engage these students. Nevertheless, some key informants adhere to traditional teaching methods by incorporating worksheets into the curriculum. The study by Hornby (2014) correlates with the findings of the study which revealed that regardless of the variations in teaching strategies utilized, all key informants share a common approach of teaching students with special needs with love, passion, and dedication. It also underscores the unwavering commitment of special education teachers to provide quality education and support to students with special needs, fostering an environment conducive to their growth and development. This strengthens assumption 2 because special education teachers use different interventions to meet the diverse needs of their students. After all, their primary goal is to cater to the diverse needs of these children by employing their chosen teaching methods effectively.

Strong relationships entail honesty, trust, mutual respect, and transparent communication between two individuals, requiring effort and compromise from both parties. They also involve reliance and interdependence on each other (Winslow, 2023). Special education teachers not only treat them as students but as their own children. The troubles that make the SPED students victims cause them to feel dreadful when they hear that their students’ were bullied. When a conflict arises, the teacher will take action to discipline. That is how far they could go for the sake of their students. Also, a bond between the teacher and the family is a need, in relation to the teacher-student problem, because the SPED teachers are eager to make their students grow, they communicate what it has to be communicated. SPED programs advocate inclusion for students with special needs; however, its full fruition has not yet come. Most students are still left out. As stated by Key informant 1, *“though sinasabi na dapat inclusive na education, hindi nal-*

left behind mga bata, dumadating pa rin talaga sa point na naleleft out sila. Masakit na kumbaga siyempre hindi lahat ng tao is open pa ang mind about sa special education. So masakit yon, in a way, challenging din siya bilang teacher, ano yung magagawa ko in order for them para 'di ma discriminate." Meanwhile, Key informants 5, 6, 7, and 8 stated that they do not feel that their students are discriminated against because their schools are inclusive, open, and accepting. Therefore, Key informants 4, 7, 9, and 10 suggested that all it takes is to spread awareness to the community for them to understand because they are not literate enough about this subject, about what it means to be a special education student, to create a more inclusive environment, and to be accepted in society. As stated by Key informant 4, *"Hindi sya discrimination actually pero matanong yung ibang bata ng bakit ganun, bakit ganyan. Hindi ko nararamdaman na nasa-sad pero yun, need sila i-educate, na kaya ganyan sya kasi may condition sya."* Teachers know much more than those bullies, so they educate them, and create a more inclusive environment. According to Adongo (2018), the family of a disabled kid or adult is probably the group that has the most knowledge about their abilities, limitations, preferred methods of learning, and character traits. For the family and the school to work together for the benefit of the child with a disability, a strong relationship is required. This strengthens assumption 5 because the majority of the key informants expressed feeling inadequate when their students face discrimination upon entering inclusive classrooms. They also noted that teachers serve as the "second parents" of the students, which makes them more affected than the students themselves when they hear negative remarks from their surroundings.

The theory developed by George Homans, the Social Exchange Theory, explains the feedback of an individual if he attempts to put in an effort and what he receives in return. It is the interaction between two variables. If they receive more than the effort they put in, they will exert more force because of what they receive in return. But if they do not get much encouragement, they might not be motivated to do the job. This is related to the aspects of job fulfillment, motivation, and dedication that SPED teachers are experiencing. Teachers feel a strong sense of vocational calling to educate special education students and leave them fulfilled as they see the outcome of teaching those students, even if it is minimal. They put in effort, time, and patience to teach those children, and in return, the improvements that the teachers see motivate them to do more, and this creates a strong relationship with students. Therefore, through social exchange theory, it is understood that when teachers feel that they are making an impact on their students, they strive to teach them and achieve the overall goal of being a SPED teacher.

Meanwhile, the Critical Theory was developed by Horkheimer, Adorno, Marcuse, and Habermas. It intends to understand how society works and how to make it better. It observes how society is set up and affects each other. It also explains why some people have more opportunities than others, which makes it unfair. This theory is relevant and helps the researchers understand its relation to the narratives of special education teachers. The research gap supports this matter. There is an unequal amount of study from the experiences of SPED. Most of the studies are foreign, while there are only a few studies tackling the local experiences of SPED. There is an imbalance, and foreign students have more studies than locals. In another context, there are different kinds of calling that the SPED teachers experienced, leading them to different levels of motivation

and passion for their students. The critical theory answers why some teachers are experiencing more difficulties than others because of the number of teachers and governmental support.

Quantia and Motus (2023) described the lived experiences of special education teachers as a mix of highs and lows, akin to a roller coaster ride. They noted that while many teachers find their work challenging yet rewarding, others consider it overwhelmingly difficult due to various obstacles. In this figure, the sense of vocational calling contributes to the aspects of job fulfillment and drive and motivation in teaching by special education teachers. Their belief that teaching these students with special needs is a divine mission strongly fuels their fervent dedication to educating these students wholeheartedly. Utilization of diverse interventions and strong relationships with their students also lead to special education as a career, as this figure delves into the different strategies that teachers employ to meet the diverse needs of their students.

Figure 2. *Challenges Faced by Special Education Teachers*

Through the interview, the researchers were able to determine the challenges faced by Special Education teachers in the first district of Laguna. The SPED teachers have their own approach in handling the challenges they face in their line of work. The researchers gathered insights from every key informant who shared their struggles while meeting the diverse needs of their students. Limited number of teachers is one of the major lacking in special education, where there are not enough teachers available to meet the needs of their students. According to Key informant 1, “*nakita ko yung kakulangan sobrang kailangan ng bansa natin ang SPED teacher so I stick to it na parang nandun na rin yung desire na kailangan kong tapusin ‘to kasi kailangan ako ng mga bata.*” As a result, Key informant 1 made the decision to remain in the field of SPED teaching, driven by her desire to make a difference because the children rely on them. She enjoyed it once she became more familiar with the SPED field. Another relevant reason that is stated by Key

informant 9, "*Kasi nga limited lang din yung teachers na knowledgeable, in terms of sign language. So, hindi lahat ay able na makapag turo. Kasi nga, it is a skill.*" There are only a few teachers who can effectively teach their students in terms of sign language, and it is really challenging for them to find SPED teachers who have special skills needed to teach students using sign language. In the study of McLeskey (2017) and Kishida (2021), the shortage of special education teachers is a significant issue in school districts worldwide, with attrition and a lack of applicants contributing to the problem. The roles and practices of special education teachers have evolved due to the complexity of struggling learners and the quest to improve outcomes.

In addition to their challenges, special education teachers encountered heavy workloads despite their dedication to their students' progress. Having heavy workloads means having a significant number of responsibilities to juggle within a specific timeframe. As stated by Key informant 10, "*So, there were pupils needing a very substantial support. Kasi napaka hirap naman ng trabaho namin. Gagawa ka pa ng mga lessons mo, gagawa ka pa ng mga visuals mo, lahat na sa iyo.*" Teaching students effectively has always been a multifaceted task just like Key informant 10 has stated, they must implement tailored strategies to support their learning. Some people believe that their salary is high, but they don't realize how challenging the job can be to which Key informant 3 answered, "*Oo, marami talaga. Akala nila... Sabihin laki-laki ng sweldo tapos ganiyan gagawin mo? Ewan ko lang kung kayanin ninyo. Kasi ang isang batang SPED talaga, lima ang katumbas.*" This was said that the difficulty of teaching should not be judged only by the number of students a teacher has. Being a special education teacher can be challenging. The workload includes extensive paperwork, low pay, and the pressure of managing disruptive behavior in a noisy classroom. The shortage of special education teachers is directly linked to high turnover and recruitment difficulties. Dealing with a large amount of paperwork, heavy workloads, and professional isolation requires a dedicated and committed individual. Without these dedicated professionals, many people struggle to overcome lifelong difficulties (AlignStaffing, 2023; Zaic, 2021). Therefore, this strengthens the assumption that the SPED teachers are under increased strain due to their working conditions.

The lack of resources is also a major problem that special education teachers often encounter. They often face shortages of materials and fundings which can include textbooks, classroom supplies, and technology. They must work hard to fill the gap and provide their students with the necessary support and opportunities to learn. To instruct properly, Key informant 2 claimed that they must even collect pieces of wood to provide chairs and other instructional materials for their students. This has been going on during their years of teaching in the institution. "*Kulang talaga sa totoo lang, in terms of the materials and the needs. Nagipon nalang ako ng mga kahoy kahoy para lang magkaroon ng chairs. Kailangan kong mag provide ng kung ano yung kaya ko, minsan out of my personal budget.*" Many participants during the interview have also shared their struggles in providing teaching materials that sometimes even involves their own budget, compensating for the lacking materials that were needed to instruct unique needs of each specialized child. Key informant 5 mentioned that "*Pagdating kasi sa teaching materials since you're catering for each child individually, it's lacking. So, di talaga maiiwasan na*

as teacher, gagamit ka ng sarili mong resources magd-DIY ka, bibili ka to compensate for the lacking materials.” Being a teacher, they cannot avoid it and end up using their own resources and buying materials to make up for what is lacking. These significant challenges have become so burdensome for the teachers like Key informant 10 that they have found themselves compelled to seek assistance from both the students' parents and the Local Government Unit (LGU) to procure essential materials to support them in their teaching endeavors. Amidst it all, despite the absence of essential resources, SPED teachers have demonstrated remarkable creativity in their teaching methods to ensure that their students receive comprehensive instruction. They have resorted to improving their own materials and integrating activities that require minimal resources, often utilizing do-it-yourself (DIY) projects to facilitate learning experiences that are both fulfilling and sustainable for the children. Effective instruction requires a great deal of work from the teachers at special education facilities. The ideas of teachers can serve as the foundation for creating laws that will support the delivery of effective services for individuals with special needs. (Guantia & Motus, 2023; Karabiyik & Avcioglu, 2021).

There have been numerous challenges that have shown when talking about the lack of teaching materials. In addition, there has consistently been a difficulty in accessing governmental support that many SPED teachers actively seek assistance with. Lack of administrative support is a situation where teachers may not receive sufficient assistance or guidance from the school administration in addressing their needs and challenges. Key informant 8 pins out her voice about the problem she encountered within her community, “*Hindi pa kasi ganun ka-tatag ang Department of Education, in terms para sa secondary. And papunta na rin sa senior high school or kung magc-college yung bata, or deployment which is mas dapat ‘yun yung priority na maibigay.*” Even though only one key informant specifically mentioned the lack of administrative support, it is apparent from the responses of the other participants that they also face challenges with the government's absence. Nevertheless, they demonstrate a strong commitment to their roles as instructors, even in the face of difficulties within their departments. According to Starks and Reich (2023), there is very little support from stakeholders for the needs of students enrolled in special education programs. Nevertheless, difficulties and issues were technically handled to preserve a cordial working environment among stakeholders, teachers, and administrators.

Conflicts within organizations, such as schools, are frequently encountered and garner attention from psychologists and educational professionals due to their significant effects on both individual and group efficacy. Root causes include the unfair distribution of resources, limited opportunities for advancement, subjective evaluations of teacher performance, non-compliance with internal protocols, and ineffective communication. Disagreements among colleagues are a frequent occurrence in any professional setting, stemming from external factors or personal conflicts. During the interview with the key informants regarding their challenges within their community include the conflict with the co-workers. It revealed different experiences in handling conflict among their co-workers. Key informant 3 mentioned, “*Wala naman. Kumbaga, dito kami sa SPED, bonded talaga. Pero kapag kunwari may problema, usap tayo ganiyan*” stating that there are no conflicts among the members of the SPED community. They have a strong bond and are always

willing to talk and resolve any issues that may arise. While Key informant 1 believed that each of them has different priorities and personalities in life, *“Nandon dapat na may mag-aadjust hindi laging parehong kami ay nasa taas, dapat may bababa talaga. Iba-iba kami ng pinaglalaman sa buhay, iba-iba kami ng mga ugali.”* Key informant 5 also talked about her challenges in her respective role as Special Education teacher, explaining about the misconception that others view their work as easier. *“Feeling nila konti ang work dahil nga we have a modified curriculum. Our paper works are different from those of regular classroom teachers. We are working just as hard as any other teacher”*. However, Key informants 2 & 9 expressed frustration due to exclusion and bullying. *“Kasi may mga times na may mga programs yung iba na hindi kami naisasama. Medyo naiinis lang ako pag may mga teachers, mapa-SPED teachers or regular teachers na parang yun bang medyo masama yung sinasabi dun sa bata”* Key informant 9 then added, *“Sometimes, students were being bullied. And the community itself does not have knowledge about sign language”* which Key informant 9 feels like the students did not have the necessary support and understanding from the community regarding their communication needs. While a few individuals provided statements about their experiences in the facility, most of the statements indicated that working with their colleagues is not as seamless as commonly perceived. On a personal level, conflicts can tarnish a teacher's reputation, lead to disinterest in educational matters, create tension, and produce a hostile atmosphere among staff, all of which detrimentally affect the educational process (Catană, 2015). The findings revealed the challenges that Special Education (SPED) teachers face when collaborating with others, stemming from factors such as differing principles, personalities, misconceptions held by regular teachers regarding the role of SPED teachers, and instances of frustration caused by bullying of students by teachers from opposing factions.

Special Education serves as a dedicated institution for children with special needs. Given the distinct challenges posed by these students, SPED teachers often face hurdles in handling their physical aggression. Their role goes beyond teaching; they also assist in managing the students' challenging behaviors and help parents learn effective strategies for handling them. Key informant 1 stated the importance of having children assessed by therapists prior to starting school. Key informant 5 also emphasized the significance of educators being knowledgeable about the specific conditions of their students to effectively support them. *“Handling kids with special needs is a challenge itself. Aside from kailangan mong aralin yung disability na ‘yon, yung intervention na gagamitin mo should be individualized. And interventions do not fit all. So minsan, related pero kailangan talagang individualized. You have to make parents your allies.”* She suggested that it involves not only studying and understanding their specific disabilities but also customizing the interventions to meet their individual needs. By involving parents as their allies in the process, they can enhance the support and care provided to their children. Exploring further into the experiences of SPED teachers in managing children with special needs in the classroom, some express the difficulty they face in dealing with their students physically. It was said by Key informant 7 that children with special conditions have different levels of aggressions; moderate, mild, and severe cases. *“May certain behavior talaga sila na uncontrollable, at masasaktan ka talaga bilang isang teacher pero dapat well prepared ka don sa mga ganon kasi hindi naman nila intentionally*

yung mga ginagawa nila. Yun yung reason kaya kung bakit tutulungan mo sila” In such situations, one approach is to closely monitor and observe the children because they may not want to be touched during their tantrums, making it challenging to provide assistance. When it comes to the teaching strategies employed by SPED teachers, some express concerns about the limited capacity to provide individual attention to students during class hours. According to Andrea Banks (2020), in special education, fostering genuine relationships with students, understanding their individual needs, and creating a positive learning environment are pivotal. Setting clear expectations, organizing engaging and inclusive lessons, and focusing on each student's strengths encourage positive behaviours and engagement. These approaches, centered on respect, understanding, and positive reinforcement, are crucial for fostering an environment where all students can thrive. Teachers must be prepared to handle these behaviors compassionately and effectively, recognizing that they are not intentional actions. Additionally, educators address the challenge of providing individualized attention within the constraints of class time and resources, further complicated by students' varying attention spans and retention levels.

This aligns with the theory of Critical Theory, developed by Max Horkheimer and Theodor Adorno, which originated from the Frankfurt School in the early 20th century (Nickerson, 2023). It explains that in special education programs, there is a significant impact of the challenges that SPED teachers face. This theory can be applied to understand how they navigate the challenges posed by limited funding, resources, and support on the quality of education. This offers a framework for analyzing how these factors impact the experiences and outcomes of special education programs. Additionally, SPED teachers face significant challenges daily, including managing students with diverse needs and dealing with physical aggression, all while working with a limited number of colleagues. These challenges are among the factors that lead to the outcomes described by George Homans in his 1958 Social Exchange Theory. This theory highlights the necessity for adequate rewards that SPED teachers desire and expect in return for their efforts. It provides a framework for analyzing the expected outcomes for SPED teachers who take on these burdens, enduring considerable costs in exchange for their service. Moreover, the Social Exchange Theory can help assess whether the relationships between SPED teachers and their benefactors are fair, valid, and still effective. Given the potential shortage of teachers resulting from insufficient rewards, despite the high costs they bear, it is clear that achieving the desired outcomes, such as students reducing their physical aggression and learning effectively, can illustrate the theory's concept of reciprocity. This give-and-take dynamic is essential for motivating SPED teachers to address the daily challenges they face.

Given the fact that Special Education teachers have a lot to handle, dealing with the uniqueness of each student and working with diverse attitudes and behaviors, it becomes crucial for effective teaching and learning in an academic setting. They navigate through various challenges such as limited number of teachers, heavy workloads, lack of resources, lack of administrative support, conflict among co-workers, and physical aggression from students, which can significantly impact the ability of teachers to provide quality education and support to their students. According to Allam and Martin (2021), it

was stated that placement of students with special needs in an inclusive classroom with ordinary students is not enough with no proper support. These students did not receive the necessary support and services to access curriculum facilities, and the support from stakeholders is minimal in meeting the needs of students enrolled in SPED classes. Issues and problems were addressed in a technical manner to maintain a positive working environment among school heads, teachers, and stakeholders. In conclusion, all participants involved encounter difficulties in managing the behaviors of the special children they work with. While some teachers develop strategies to address aggressive attitudes, it is important to recognize the ongoing challenges faced by all special education teachers. They consistently strive to create a safe and supportive learning environment for their students, demonstrating their unwavering dedication to their profession.

Figure 3. *Collaboration with Parents and Professionals*

Consultation, as defined by Cambridge University (n.d.), meets with others in order to get advice from them, which, as per the Key Informants, is crucial in accommodating the children’s special needs. A literature by Arkansas State University (2016) entitled “Importance of Collaboration in Special Education,” underscores the need for collaboration of special education teachers with other experts to accommodate the special needs of the students. This was further expounded by the key informants. During the interviews, the key informants talked about how integral collaboration with specialists and experts is. “*Oo, napaka importante kasi, in order for us to be successful sa pagbibigay*

ng service dun sa bata.” Key Informant 1 said. Likewise, according to Key Informant 2, *“Syempre malaking bagay yung collaboration. Napaka-limited, kung tutuusin, napakalimited ng kaalaman naming SPED teacher doon sa mga bagay na dapat pa naming malaman sa special education. So nakiki-pag collaborate kami.”*— expressing how profound collaboration is on the special education teachers. There are also times when special education teachers are able to do what most professionals can, but can’t do the same with other professionals. *“Yung mga ginagawa ng OT minsan na gagawa na rin ng SPED teachers. Pero yung sa speech therapist, siyempre, ‘di naman namin pwedeng gawin,”* Key Informant 6 expressed. Their limited knowledge on certain areas requires collaboration with experts and professionals to know more, which can then enable them to handle and fulfill the students’ special needs. In addition, Key Informant 1 emphasized the importance of having a connection with other professionals for seeking advice and help. Key Informant 5 and 10 often engage in a practice they refer to as “team teaching” or “co-teaching,” wherein they collaborate with other special education teachers, utilizing their strengths to better educate the children and meet their educational needs. Moreover, special education has IEP (Individualized Education Plan) reviews and meetings to meet with parents, regular teachers, and other multidisciplinary professionals. IEP meetings can look over the children’s behavior and the ones they still need to improve. *“Nagkaroon kami ng meeting. Gumawa kami ng IEP non, kumbaga nandoon makikita yung behavior ng mga bata, yung mga kailangan pa nilang i-improve,”* Key Informant 7 informed. Furthermore, special education teachers collaborate with other professionals to ask for advice and learn on how to calm down the child and what activities they can give. They also said there are other teachers who are inclusive that they become teamed-up with to ask questions pertaining the performance of the students with special needs. However, despite the fact that other key informants collaborate and consult with other professionals, Key Informant 9 expressed the unnecessary need of their students for such therapy and other services. *“Based on my students, they don’t need to undergo occupational therapist and other related services,”* Key Informant 9 said. Also, Key Informant 7 gave an instance where their multi-disciplinary team takes advice from parents and teachers on what the special education teachers can do in their classroom. With this, the findings strengthen the 6th Assumption of the study, stating “The SPED teachers collaborate with professionals such as psychotherapists and other teachers to support students with special needs. The findings are also aligned with a literature by Arkansas State University (2016) entitled “Importance of Collaboration in Special Education,” which highlights the need for collaboration of special education teachers with other experts to accommodate the special needs of the students.

The interviews held with the special education teachers revealed the importance of honest, frequent, and daily communication with parents for them to be updated regarding their children. This entails that both the teacher and the parent are involved in a reciprocal process, where they communicate to make the students’ needs known, and others communicate back to acknowledge and respond to their needs. Moreover, the special education teachers have Parent-Teacher Conferences and IEP (Individualized Education Plan) reviews and meetings. Key Informant 5 stated that they conduct IEP reviews every quarter, while Key informant 4 and Key informant 10 explained that they use parent-teacher conferences to update the parents on their children. *“Every quarter,*

meron din kaming parent-teacher conference,” Key Informant 4 said and Key Informant 10 added, *“Parent-teacher conference, normally, ang ginagawa ko.”* Also, Key Informant 10, at times, makes use of what they call “coffee table talk,” where Key Informant 10 discusses topics and gives updates to the parents of their children with special needs along with coffee. *“Sometimes, I do what I call coffee table talk. So, may ilang topics ako id-discuss sa kanila, tapos, I will give them updates and also literally may pa-kape kasi coffee table talk nga siya,”* Key Informant 10 said. Meanwhile, Key Informant 9 differentiated by responding, *“I always conducted one-on-one interaction with the parents after the class.”* Correspondingly, negative encounters with the parents are present, such as Key Informant 10 stating that sometimes parents can be stubborn and don't understand that they're too confident and too hopeful that everything is expected of the teacher. *“Minsan ma titigas din yung ulo ng parents. They do not understand and sometimes masyado na silang kampante at masyadong pala-asa, na lahat na ay iaasa,”* Key Informant 10 said. Nevertheless, there are positive encounters in which the special education teachers communicate with the parents by giving them advice, feedback, and updates concerning their children. Findings founded alignment with the Assumption #1 of the study, where it states “The SPED teachers have developed close relationships with parents that help learning among students.” Also, the findings support a study by Adongo (2018), emphasizing the importance of strong connection between the family and the school to collaborate and work together for the benefit of the child with a disability.

With special education teachers collaborating and communicating with parents, and other professionals or experts, feedback can be inferred. Essentially, feedback informs the parents about what's going on with their children, their behavior, their performance, and also gives the parents reminders, advice, and daily updates. Key Informant 4, after class, gives feedback and updates to the parents on what their child did that day, academically and behavior-wise. *“After every class, feedback to parents– kung ano yung mga ginawa nila sa school that day, academics and behaviors,”* Key Informant 4 said. Similarly, Key Informant 3, 5, and 8 does the same by updating the parents on what is happening with their child and says what to do. Also, Key Informant 7 gives the parents instructions or if they need to talk regarding their child. A collective attitude of feedback to the parents about their children suggests an environment where working together and communication promotes child support, development, and overall well-being. In addition, Key Informant 6 emphasizes on having a positive outlook towards their child and suggests applying the programs implemented in the schools. *“Binibigyan ko na lang sila ng advice na syempre, kailangan maging laging positive ang outlook sa mga bata. In-aadvice ko sila sa mga pwede nilang gawin at yung mga program din na pagdating sa program dito sa school, pwede rin naman apply sa bahay nila,”* according to Key Informant 6. Likewise, Key Informant 9 reminds the parents to follow-up the children on their studies while observing their performances at home. The interviews also revealed that some special education teachers ask for progress reports and annual assessments from other professionals. *“We usually ask for progress reports from other professionals like therapists. Pagdating naman sa developmental pediatrician, actually po nire-require namin ang student to atleast have uhm, latest assessment every year,”* Key Informant 5 said. Similarly, Key Informant 3 stated a doctor, at times comes over to assess the concerns of the children. *“Tapos minsan may mga napunta rin ditong doktor,*

concern nila is para sa mga bata, puro assessment lang 'yon,” Key Informant 3 said. Furthermore, Key Informant 4 has a center in their school like a clinic where there is a SPED specialist. They said, *“So, needed namin din sya to work, here din sa school mismo, sa center, meron kaming SPED specialist.”* University of South Carolina (n.d.) expresses the importance of feedback in the learning process to enable the student to improve and not hinder them. Which further emphasizes that feedback is crucial to the development of the student, along with the findings.

The interviews held with the special education teachers in the first district of Laguna presented findings such as collaboration with parents and other experts or specialists to fulfill the students' special needs by communicating with them. The findings support two of these theories for the study used— Social Exchange Theory, wherein special education teachers' relationships with the parents and to other experts. By examining how these factors influence negative encounters with parents, parent-teacher conference, consultation with experts/specialist and day to day feedback and assessments. Researchers can gain crucial insights into the lived experiences of these educators and ultimately contribute to the development and well-being of the children with special needs as well as to a positive change within the field of special education. In Critical Theory, It emphasizes critical self-reflection and amplifies the voices of marginalized groups. Special education teachers frequently navigate challenging situations and unseen battles within the educational system. This framework allows researchers to analyze these experiences and give voice to the teachers' perspectives. By doing so, the research can contribute to positive systemic change within the educational landscape.

Effective communication is vital as it allows involved parties to know one another, as well as participate and listen to one another (Buckner, 2023). The statements from key informants highlight the key role of communication in establishing connections between parents, and students with special needs, as well as educators with other experts or specialists. Also, the findings emphasize the significance of collaboration with professionals and experts in addressing the special needs of students. In addition, special education teachers recognize the value of seeking advice, sharing knowledge, and working collectively to ensure the quality of education to the students. Whether through parent-teacher conferences, IEP reviews, or multi-disciplinary team meetings, these all contribute to a better education and support for the students with special needs. Despite challenges such as stubborn parents, special education teachers are committed and passionate about what they do. Moreover, with feedback such as daily updates, reminders, advice, and progress reports, not only keep parents informed, but also builds a collaborative environment for supporting the development and well-being of the students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings in the research study, it was revealed how special education teachers view their profession as a career, providing different perspectives when it comes to the sense of vocational calling, which presents the reason for their unyielding motivation to teach potentially resulting from job satisfaction. It can also be concluded that special education teachers are building strong relationships with students with special needs. This not only helps them effectively teach the students but also facilitates smoother interactions between the students. In line with this, teachers employ a variety of interventions tailored to each learner's specific learning needs. Furthermore, it was also mentioned that special education teachers are encountering different challenges within their educational field, such as conflict among co-workers, which is disclosed to be a fight regarding the treatment of other students, and physical aggression from the students, which is a result of their unique cases and conditions. Following this, they also experienced a lack of administrative support resulting in a limited number of teachers causing heavy workloads. The lack of resources in their institution has resulted in them making their own instructional materials and using their own budget. Moreover, the study highlighted the vital collaboration between special education teachers, parents, and professionals to ensure effective instruction. Despite facing challenges, special education teachers illustrated instances of strained interactions with parents. To address these issues, they employed strategies like parent-teacher conferences where they state to the parents the improvement and behaviors of their children during classes and sought advice from experts to provide daily feedback on children's assessments, emphasizing the importance of ongoing communication and partnership in optimizing educational outcomes for students with special needs.

Recommendations

The findings of the study infer the following set of recommendations: (1) The special education teachers will serve as a way that would create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment by regularly assessing their student needs, collaborating with parents and colleagues, and incorporating innovative teaching methods and assistive technologies to maximize student learning and success; (2) The parents of students with special needs must be open to communication channels between special education teachers to foster collaboration and support; (3) The students with special needs have to ensure they receive the inclusive environment necessary for their academic and personal development; (4) The government and division offices should consider implementing focused interventions, such as inclusivity workshops for special education teachers in the cities of San Pedro, Biñan, and Sta. Rosa. These workshops aim to educate regular teachers, parents of students with special needs, and government officials about the current conditions of special education teachers and how they can contribute to establishing a safer and more inclusive environment for both teachers and students. Also, they should provide support systems to enhance the experiences of both special

education teachers and students, and; (5) The future researchers must encourage further research in the field of special education to build upon the findings of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In research, protecting the rights and well-being of key informants is vital. Obtaining the **consent, anonymity, and confidentiality** of the key informants is of utmost importance. A written agreement provided by the researchers includes seeking permissions to record, acquiring consent, maintaining confidentiality and anonymity, and committing to a set time and place. The researchers will attain the consent and willingness of the special education teachers to participate. Additionally, researchers must be meticulous in protecting the identities of key informants, safeguarding them from potential harm or unintended consequences.

In compliance with Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers ensure that personal data remains secure and is used exclusively for research purposes, preventing any unauthorized disclosure that may compromise the privacy of the key informants. All in all, receiving consent and managing anonymity and confidentiality is a commitment to ethical conduct in research, strengthening the foundation of trust between researchers and key informants.

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